

FACTORS INFLUENCING BIG DATA ANALYTICS IN PUBLIC SECTOR: A QUICK OVERVIEW

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Abstract

With the rising amounts of generated data, the need for robust and effective analytics tools has emerged. Because of that Big Data Analytics (BDA) has become a key pillar for many business firms to achieve competitive advantage over competitors. Also, many governments try to leverage (BDA) to improve decision making in a way that leads to improve productivity and provide better services for the citizens. Therefore, many research works have been dedicated for BDA in many different fields, such as supply chain management, marketing, health care, education and public services, however, the topic of BDA is still in its nascent stage, and there are many issues that need to be addressed and investigated. The current research in progress tries to shed some light about one of these issues, by answering the question “what facilitates, and hinders the adoption of BDA in the public sector?”. A review of relevant literature was conducted to answer the question, the review revealed that (data quality, leadership, privacy and analytical talent) are the most influential factors that impact BDA adoption in the public sector. The outcome of this review process constitutes a good foundation for further empirical investigation, which will be the next stage of this research.

1 INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, huge amounts of data are being generated by e-commerce web sites, social media, IoT devices and others; the type of data that is characterised by its voluminous size, fast generations rates and different data types (text, images, sensor readings, CCTV streams and so on) are known as Big Data[1]. The term (Big Data) was introduced to refer to the data volumes that is increased massively, to the level that makes it very difficult to store, process, and analyse them using traditional data base systems[2]. Most organizations maintain data repositories that contains keep track of almost everything about the organization, its people, and its environment; those repositories offers an opportunity for the organizations to observe and to create useful insights about the organization and its environment [3].

BDA id defined as “a holistic approach to manage, process and analyze the “5 Vs” data-related dimensions (i.e., volume, variety, velocity, veracity and value) in order to create actionable insights for sustained value delivery, measuring performance and establishing competitive advantages”[4]. Because of the promising improvements that BDA can offer, both private and public organizations are moving towards embracing BDA as main component of their IT infrastructure, though the pace of BDA adoption in government organizations is clearly slower than in the business private organizations; as a result, there

is much fewer studies about BDA adoption in public sector.

In this research in progress, we'll try to contribute to the body of literature by investigating the factors that affect the adoption of BDA in the public sector.

The ultimate goal of this study is to provide clearer image about the factors that affect BDA adoption in the context of public sector, in a way that guide practitioners to better practices.

2 PROPOSED WORK

The purpose of this paper is to summarize the most influential factors that facilitate or restrain the implementation of BDA in the public organizations. This is to fill in a gap in the extant literature, whereby most of the studies focus on BDA in different fields other than public sector.

Despite the opportunities that BDA can offer for governments, there are serious challenges that must be faced, and threats that need to be eliminated[5]. The current research is in its early stage, at this stage it is required to have a good background about the research area, therefore, the aim of the current paper is to extract the most BDA influential factors that were identified by other researchers. Those factors will be filtered in the next research stages based on their relevant to the study domain which is the Malaysian public sector.

Based on the initial findings of our literature review summarized below, we suggest the following model for BDA successful implementation; we expect to modify the model to include more factors, or to explain any existent mediation and/or moderation effects, after more comprehensive review of literature, and after we conduct the exploratory interviews in the coming research stages.

Figure 1 Proposed Research Model

3 RESULTS

The initial findings of our review of relevant literature is summarized in the following table, the early indications show that data quality, leadership, privacy and analytical talent are the most important determinants of the success or failure of any BDA implementation project. This list of factors is going to be the basis for further investigation, the next stage of the research will be qualitative in nature, whereby exploratory interviews will be conducted with some public-sector officials to gain better knowledge about the factors influencing BDA adoption and success in the public sector.

It is expected that the outcome of this research, which is the research model that reflects the most influential factors on BDA adoption in the public-sector context, will provide very useful insights that will help -hopefully- the ongoing efforts to adopt BDA in the Malaysian public sector.

Table 1 : List of Factors Affecting BDA Adoption

Factors	Reference
Data ownership	[6]
Data quality	[6] [7] [8] [9]
Privacy	[6] [7]
public sector’s ability to attract big data analyst talent.	[6]
BDA management capabilities	[8]
BDA technology capabilities	[8]
BDA talent capabilities	[8] [6] [9]
Organizational capabilities	[5]
Organizational alignment	[5]
Organizational maturity	[5]
Difficulty of using data collected for certain purpose, for other purposes	[7]
High cost	[10]
Executive Support (Leadership)	[10] [9]
Risk management	[10]
Lack of methodological basis	[10]
Complexity of data integration	[10]
Data security	[10]
Enterprise wide implementation	[9]
Well defined targets	[9]

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